

ISSN: 3060-4613

MAKTABGACHA
VA MAKTAB
TA'LIMI VAZIRLIGI

O'zbekiston
Milliy Pedagogika
Universiteti

№4(5)
2026

- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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Pedagogika, psixologiya fanlariga ixtisoslashgan ilmiy jurnal

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Elektron nashr. 416 sahifa,
27-aprel, 2026-yil.

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Pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha: OAK Kengashi tavsiyasi (26.08.2024-y., №11-05-4381/01) asosida:

- Ekspert kengashi (29.10.2024-y., №10)
- Rayosat qarori (31.10.2024-y., №363/5)

Psixologiya fanlari bo'yicha: Toshkent davlat pedagogika universiteti murojaatiga asosan OAK tavsiyasi (24.04.2025-y., №11-05-2566/01):

- Ekspert kengashi (25.05.2025-y., №10)
- Rayosat qarori (08.05.2025-y., №370/5)

“Maktabgacha va maktab ta’limi”
jurnali

26.09.2023-yildan

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti
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va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar
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reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha
ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: **№136361**

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THE IMPACT OF COLLABORATIVE WRITING ACTIVITIES ON EFL UNIVERSITY STUDENTS' ESSAY WRITING SKILLS: A CLASSROOM-BASED STUDY

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Abstract: This article examines the effectiveness of collaborative writing activities in improving essay writing skills among first-year EFL university students. The relevance of the study lies in the need to enhance students' academic writing competence in modern language education. The aim of the research is to determine the impact of collaborative writing on students' writing performance. A classroom-based experimental approach was used, involving control and experimental groups. The author's approach is based on integrating peer interaction and collaborative tasks into the writing process. The results show significant improvement in grammar, organization, and idea development among students in the experimental group. The scientific novelty of the study lies in applying collaborative writing as a structured pedagogical tool in EFL classrooms. The findings confirm the effectiveness of collaborative learning in improving writing skills.

Key words: collaborative writing, EFL, essay writing, peer interaction, academic writing, language learning.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada birinchi kurs EFL talabalarining esse yozish ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishda hamkorlikda yozish faoliyatlarining samaradorligi tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqotning dolzarbligi zamonaviy ta'limda talabalar yozma nutqini rivojlantirish zarurati bilan izohlanadi. Tadqiqotning maqsadi hamkorlikda yozishning talabalar yozish natijalariga ta'sirini aniqlashdan iborat. Tadqiqotda eksperimental metod qo'llanilib, nazorat va tajriba guruhlarini ishtirok etdi. Muallifning yondashuvi yozish jarayoniga interaktiv va hamkorlik elementlarini joriy etishga asoslangan. Natijalar tajriba guruhida grammatik aniqlik, tuzilma va mazmun rivojlanganini ko'rsatdi. Tadqiqotning ilmiy yangiligi hamkorlikda yozish metodini tizimli pedagogik vosita sifatida qo'llash bilan izohlanadi. Olingan natijalar ushbu metodning samaradorligini tasdiqlaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: hamkorlikda yozish, EFL, esse yozish, yozish ko'nikmalari, interaksiya, akademik yozuv.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается эффективность совместного письма в развитии навыков написания эссе у студентов первого курса EFL. Актуальность исследования обусловлена необходимостью совершенствования академического письма студентов. Цель исследования – определить влияние совместного письма на результаты письменной деятельности. В работе использован экспериментальный метод с контрольной и экспериментальной группами. Авторский подход основан на интеграции взаимодействия и совместной деятельности в процесс письма. Результаты показали значительное улучшение грамматики, структуры и содержания текстов. Научная новизна исследования заключается в применении совместного письма как педагогического инструмента. Полученные результаты подтверждают эффективность данного подхода.

Ключевые слова: совместное письмо, EFL, навыки письма, академическое письмо, взаимодействие.

INTRODUCTION

In modern language education, the development of students' writing skills has become one of the most actual and complex tasks. Writing, particularly in academic contexts, requires not only linguistic competence but also the ability to organize ideas logically, maintain coherence and cohesion, and apply appropriate grammatical structures. For learners of English as a Foreign Language (EFL), essay writing presents significant challenges due to limited vocabulary, insufficient writing practice, and the lack of effective instructional approaches. In many cases, traditional teaching methods focus primarily on individual writing tasks, which restrict opportunities for interaction, feedback, and collaborative learning.

The relevance of this study is determined by the growing need to introduce innovative pedagogical approaches that can improve students' academic writing skills and increase their engagement in the learning process. Collaborative writing, as an interactive and student-centered approach, provides learners with opportunities to exchange ideas, receive peer feedback, and jointly construct knowledge. Such interaction not only

enhances linguistic competence but also develops critical thinking and communication skills, which are essential in modern education.

Within this context, the object of the research is the process of developing essay writing skills among EFL university students, while the subject of the research focuses on the use of collaborative writing activities as a pedagogical tool for improving students' writing performance. The aim of the study is to investigate the effectiveness of collaborative writing activities in enhancing essay writing skills of first-year EFL students. In order to achieve this aim, the study addresses several key tasks, including analyzing theoretical approaches to collaborative writing, examining the role of peer interaction in the writing process, comparing collaborative and traditional writing methods, evaluating students' writing performance based on experimental data, and identifying the advantages and limitations of collaborative writing activities.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The issue of developing writing skills in EFL contexts has been widely studied by both foreign and local researchers. One of the key theoretical foundations of collaborative learning is based on the social constructivist theory proposed by Vygotsky, who emphasized that learning occurs through social interaction and cooperation within the Zone of Proximal Development ^[1]. According to this perspective, learners achieve higher levels of understanding when they work collaboratively rather than individually. This theoretical framework has become the basis for many modern pedagogical approaches, including collaborative writing.

Foreign scholars have extensively explored the role of collaborative writing in language learning. Harmer [2] highlights that writing is a process-oriented activity involving planning, drafting, revising, and editing, and each stage can be significantly enhanced through peer interaction. Hyland ^[3] also emphasizes that collaborative writing contributes to the development of coherence, cohesion, and grammatical accuracy, as students are exposed to multiple perspectives and language forms. Similarly, Storch ^[5] found that learners engaged in collaborative writing tasks produce texts with higher linguistic accuracy and better organization compared to those working individually. Swain's Output Hypothesis further supports this idea by suggesting that language production helps learners notice gaps in their knowledge and refine their linguistic competence ^[6].

In addition, Richards and Renandya ^[4] underline the importance of interaction in language teaching methodologies, stating that collaborative activities promote active learning and improve communicative competence. Johnson and Johnson ^[7] also note that cooperative learning increases students' motivation, responsibility, and academic achievement. These studies collectively confirm that collaborative writing is not only beneficial for linguistic development but also for cognitive and social skills. At the same time, local researchers have also contributed to the understanding of interactive and student-centered learning approaches. Uzbek scholars emphasize the importance of integrating modern pedagogical technologies into the educational process to enhance students' independent thinking and communicative abilities. Research in the national context highlights that traditional teaching methods still dominate in many classrooms, which limits students' opportunities for interaction and practical language use. Therefore, the introduction of collaborative learning approaches, including collaborative writing, is considered a necessary step in improving the quality of education.

Despite the considerable number of studies on collaborative writing, there are still certain gaps in the research. Many studies focus primarily on general language development, while insufficient attention is given to its specific impact on essay writing skills in EFL university contexts. Furthermore, the application of collaborative writing in local educational settings has not been sufficiently explored through experimental research. Thus, the originality of the present study lies in its focus on the effectiveness of collaborative writing activities specifically for improving essay writing skills among first-year EFL university students through a classroom-based experimental design. The study not only analyzes theoretical approaches but also provides empirical evidence based on practical implementation, which distinguishes it from previous research. Collaborative learning has also been shown to increase students' motivation and responsibility in the learning process ^[7]. In addition, principles of language learning emphasize the importance of interaction and practice in skill development ^[8].

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A total of 30 first-year university students participated in the study and were divided into two groups: a control group and an experimental group, each consisting of 15 students. The control group followed traditional individual writing practices, while the experimental group engaged in structured collaborative writing activities. The experiment was conducted over a period of six weeks, during which both groups were assigned essay writing tasks under different instructional conditions.

The research methodology included the use of a comparative approach to analyze differences in students' performance between the two groups. Specifically, pre-test and post-test essays were administered to assess

students' writing skills at the beginning and end of the study. These essays were evaluated using a standardized rubric based on key criteria such as content development, organization, grammatical accuracy, and vocabulary usage.

In the experimental group, collaborative writing activities were implemented through various stages, including group brainstorming, joint drafting, peer editing, and revision. This process allowed students to interact, exchange ideas, and provide feedback to each other. In contrast, the control group completed writing tasks individually without collaborative support.

The collected data were analyzed using quantitative methods, including the calculation of average scores and comparison of performance indicators between the two groups. The results of the analysis made it possible to identify the effectiveness of collaborative writing activities and determine their impact on students' writing development. Thus, the applied methodology ensured the reliability and validity of the research findings by combining experimental design, comparative analysis, and systematic evaluation of students' writing performance.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The analysis of the collected data was carried out based on the results of pre-test and post-test assessments in order to evaluate the effectiveness of collaborative writing activities in improving students' essay writing skills. The data obtained from both the control and experimental groups were compared using quantitative methods, particularly by calculating average scores and identifying differences in performance indicators.

The initial pre-test results showed that both groups had nearly identical levels of writing proficiency, with the control group scoring an average of 62 and the experimental group scoring 61. This indicates that both groups started at a similar level, which ensures the reliability of the experimental comparison. After the implementation of the instructional intervention over a six-week period, the post-test results demonstrated noticeable improvement in both groups; however, the degree of improvement differed significantly. The control group, which followed traditional individual writing practices, showed a moderate increase from 62 to 68. In contrast, the experimental group, which participated in collaborative writing activities, showed a substantial increase from 61 to 78.

These results clearly indicate that collaborative writing has a stronger positive impact on students' writing performance compared to traditional methods. The improvement observed in the experimental group can be attributed to several factors. First, collaborative writing provided students with opportunities to exchange ideas and engage in meaningful discussions, which contributed to better content development. Second, peer feedback allowed students to identify and correct grammatical errors more effectively. Third, working in groups enhanced students' motivation and engagement, which played a crucial role in improving overall performance.

As shown in the statistical data, the difference in post-test scores between the two groups highlights the effectiveness of collaborative learning strategies. The experimental group not only improved in terms of grammatical accuracy but also demonstrated better organization, coherence, and vocabulary usage in their essays.

Figure 1: Comparison of Pre-test and Post-test Results between Control and Experimental Groups

The graphical representation of the results further illustrates the significant difference in performance between the control and experimental groups. As shown in Figure 1, the experimental group achieved a higher level of improvement compared to the control group, which confirms the effectiveness of collaborative writing activities.

In addition to the quantitative analysis, qualitative observations revealed several important aspects. Students in the experimental group were more actively involved in the learning process, demonstrated better problem-solving skills, and showed increased confidence in expressing their ideas in written form. However, some challenges were also identified, such as unequal participation among group members and difficulties in time management during collaborative tasks.

Overall, the analysis of the results indicates that while traditional methods can lead to gradual improvement, collaborative writing provides a more effective and interactive approach to developing writing skills. The findings highlight the importance of integrating collaborative learning strategies into EFL classrooms to achieve better educational outcomes.

CONCLUSION

Based on the analysis of the research findings, it can be concluded that collaborative writing activities have a significant positive impact on the development of essay writing skills among first-year EFL university students. The results of the study demonstrated that students who participated in collaborative writing tasks showed greater improvement in terms of grammatical accuracy, organization, coherence, and idea development compared to those who followed traditional individual writing methods. This confirms that interactive and student-centered approaches are more effective in enhancing writing competence in EFL contexts.

The findings also revealed that collaborative writing not only improves linguistic performance but also contributes to the development of essential cognitive and social skills. Students involved in collaborative activities became more engaged in the learning process, demonstrated higher motivation, and developed better critical thinking and communication abilities. At the same time, the study identified certain challenges, such as unequal participation among group members and difficulties related to time management, which may affect the overall effectiveness of collaborative tasks if not properly addressed.

Based on these results, several practical recommendations can be proposed. First, it is advisable for teachers to integrate collaborative writing activities into regular classroom practice in order to enhance students' writing performance. Second, structured peer feedback should be incorporated into writing tasks to ensure active participation of all students and to improve the quality of written work. Third, teachers should provide clear guidelines and assign specific roles within groups to minimize unequal participation and improve task organization. Additionally, it is recommended to combine collaborative writing with traditional methods to achieve a balanced and comprehensive approach to writing instruction.

Furthermore, educational institutions should support the implementation of collaborative learning strategies by providing appropriate training for teachers and creating a learning environment that encourages interaction and cooperation. Future research may focus on exploring the long-term effects of collaborative writing and its integration with digital tools and online learning platforms.

In conclusion, collaborative writing can be considered an effective pedagogical tool that not only enhances students' writing skills but also promotes active learning, cooperation, and overall academic development.

References:

1. Vygotsky, L.S. (1978). *Mind in Society: The Development of Higher Psychological Processes*. Harvard University Press.
2. Harmer, J. (2004). *How to Teach Writing*. London: Longman.
3. Hyland, K. (2003). *Second Language Writing*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
4. Richards, J.C., & Renandya, W.A. (2002). *Methodology in Language Teaching: An Anthology of Current Practice*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
5. Storch, N. (2005). Collaborative writing: Product, process, and students' reflections. *Journal of Second Language Writing*, 14(3), 153–173.
6. Swain, M. (2000). The output hypothesis and beyond: Mediating acquisition through collaborative dialogue. In J.P. Lantolf (Ed.), *Sociocultural Theory and Second Language Learning* (pp. 97–114). Oxford University Press.
7. Johnson, D.W., & Johnson, R.T. (1999). *Learning Together and Alone: Cooperative, Competitive, and Individualistic Learning*. Boston: Allyn & Bacon.
8. Brown, H.D. (2007). *Principles of Language Learning and Teaching*. Pearson Education.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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2026. №4(5)

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"Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi" jurnali 26.09.2023-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №C-5669363 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.
Litsenziya raqami: № 136361.

Manzirimiz: Toshkent shahar, Yunusobod tumani
19-mavze, 17-uy.